

Low-Power and High-Throughput LUT-based Accelerator Architecture for Distributed CNN Inference at the Edge

Authors: [Quentin Dariol](#), [Domenik Helms](#)

German Aerospace Center (DLR), Institute for Systems Engineering and future mobility (SE), Oldenburg, Germany.

Contact: quentin.dariol@dlr.de

I. Motivation

Challenges:

- Implementing Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) at the edge due to computational and memory demands versus resource limitations.
- Distributed AI inference at edge key to allow novel applications in multiple domains [1] e.g. future mobility and aerospace.

Key concepts of the proposed approach:

- LUT-Based HW accelerators: Store CNN layers as Look-Up Tables (LUTs) in FPGA, removing the need for external memory and enabling fast, energy efficient inference.
- Specification of an ecosystem to enable distributed CNN inference at edge involving multiple systems.

II. Ecosystem for distributed inference

• **A.1 HW:** Ensures high throughput and energy efficiency with FPGA-based AI accelerators near data sensors.

• **A.2 SW:** Hypervisor and scheduler - Manage access of high-level SW applications to HW accelerators, leveraging power management techniques and Dynamic Partial Reconfiguration (DPR).

• **B AI applications** - Manage access of high-level SW applications to HW accelerators, leveraging power management techniques and Dynamic Partial Reconfiguration (DPR).

• **C Networking:** The system must also be able to locate and network with nearby systems, and update its network map.

III. LUT-based accelerator architecture using ElasticAI [2] / LUTNet [3] framework

- Originality: pre-computed weights are synthesized as LUTs, allowing to remove external memory access.
- Evaluation results on Conv-1D electrocardiogram recognition on Spartan S15 FPGA. **Resource Usage:** 40% LUTs, no block RAM or DSP. **Performance:** Throughput of 10 million samples/second, energy cost of 26.2 nJ/sample.

IV. Prospects

- Enable support for Conv-2D, critical for complex applications.
- Address resource utilization issues, and low prediction accuracy.

[1] S. Laskaridis et al. The Future of Consumer Edge-AI Computing. 2023. arXiv: 2210.10514 [cs.LG].

[2] C. Qian et al. "ElasticAI: Creating and Deploying Energy Efficient Deep Learning Accelerator for Pervasive Computing". In: IEEE International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications. Open source release. 2023. URL: <https://github.com/es-ude/elastic-ai.creator>

[3] D. Helms et al. "FPGA-Based Low Latency, Low Power Stream Processing AI". In: European Workshop on On-Board Data Processing. 2021.